

Effect of Independent Additions of Inorganic Salts of Nitrogen, Phosphorus and Sulphur on Sulphur Mineralisation of the Native Organic Matter in Soil

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Laboratory incubation studies were conducted on the effect of independent additions of $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, KH_2PO_4 and K_2SO_4 on the mineralisation of sulphur in two soils. Sulphur mineralisation was found to be related to the initial sulphate sulphur and organic sulphur content of the soils. Addition of $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ widens the N : S ratio and resulted immobilisation of sulphur in soil. Depending upon the initial sulphate sulphur content of the soil, addition of KH_2PO_4 or K_2SO_4 either stimulates or inhibits the net mineralisation of sulphur contained in the native organic matter in soil.

RESULTS of his experiment led Barrow¹ to suggest that mineralisation of sulphur depends on the concentration of other elements. However, there are few reports on the effect of varying supply of other nutrient ions on the mineralisation or immobilisation of sulphur. In another study Barrow² observed considerable increase in the extractable sulphate when urea was incubated with a soil. Kwalenko and Lowe³ reported that addition of nitrogen resulted decrease in sulphur mineralisation during 8 week period of incubation.

Sulphur deficiency in agricultural soils of West Bengal has been increased in recent years due to the decreased use of sulphur containing fertilisers (ammonium sulphate, super phosphate and potassium sulphate) and intensive cropping. Mukhopadhyay and Mukhopadhyay⁴ also observed that inorganic sulphate sulphur content of the non-saline soils (0-15 cm) of West Bengal varies from 0.6 ppm to 27.5 ppm. Hence use of sulphur as fertiliser element and studies on the factors influencing its mineralisation are of considerable importance. Using tracer technique Sachdev and Chhabra⁵ observed that 68.1% of the added sulphur was present as sulphate sulphur in an alluvial soil even after four months period of incubation under aerobic

condition. In view of the above a laboratory incubation was, therefore, conducted to study the independent addition of inorganic salts of nitrogen, phosphorus and sulphur on sulphur mineralisation from the native organic matter in the soil.

Experimental

The study was conducted on two soils (0-15 cm layer samples) collected from Mundabasti in Darjeeling district of the sub-Himalayan Hill region and Chinsurah in Hooghly district of the Gangetic Alluvial region. After collection, the soils were ground to pass through 0.5 mm sieve. Relevant characteristics of the soils are presented in Table 1.

For the laboratory incubation study, 25 g of each of the two soil samples was taken in a glass container and to which the respective treatment materials were separately added and allowed to incubate at laboratory room temperature ($30 \pm 5^\circ$) under 50% of the moisture holding capacity. Loss of moisture due to evaporation was adjusted by addition of water on every alternate day. Separate and duplicate samples for each treatment was maintained for each of the five sampling stages corresponding to 15, 30, 45, 60 and 75 days of incubation.

TABLE 1—PROPERTIES OF THE SOILS

Soil samples collected from	pH (1 : 2.5)	% water holding capacity	% organic carbon	% total nitrogen	% total sulphur	Organic sulphur (ppm)	0.15 % CaCl_2 extractable sulphate sulphur (ppm)	N : S
Mundabasti	4.9	68	3.14	0.424	0.0219	218.1	0.6	19.3
Chinsurah	6.0	32	0.77	0.071	0.0062	49.7	12.8	11.4

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF INORGANIC SALT OF NITROGEN ADDITION ON SULPHUR MINERALISATION

Soil samples collected from	Levels of N-added (ppm)	S-mineralised (ppm)									
		Incubation periods in days									
		15		30		45		60		75	
		A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B
Mundabasti	200	1.25	-4.37	0	-2.19	0	-2.81	0	-3.44	0.31	-2.81
	100	1.56	-3.12	0.16	-2.03	0	-2.81	1.25	-2.19	0.31	-2.81
Chinsurah	200	1.25	-14.37	3.75	-5.63	1.87	-6.57	1.12	-5.75	0.62	-7.19
	100	0.94	-14.68	0	-9.38	0	-8.44	0.16	-6.77	2.19	-5.62

A = Sulphate sulphur content

B = Increase of sulphate sulphur over control.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF INORGANIC SALT OF PHOSPHORUS ADDITION ON SULPHUR MINERALISATION

Soil samples collected from	Levels of P-added (ppm)	S-mineralised (ppm)									
		Incubation period in days									
		15		30		45		60		75	
		A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B
Mundabasti	200	2.50	-3.12	0.62	-1.57	0.47	-2.84	0.62	-2.82	0.94	-2.18
	100	2.81	-2.81	2.19	0	2.50	-0.31	2.19	-1.25	1.56	-1.56
Chinsurah	200	19.37	3.75	20.00	10.62	12.50	4.06	—	—	9.69	1.88
	100	12.19	-3.43	13.12	3.74	18.12	9.68	10.62	3.75	13.12	5.31

A = Sulphate sulphur content

B = Increase of sulphate sulphur over control.

Besides an untreated control there were six other treatments adopted for the present investigation. Each of the three sources of nitrogen, phosphorus and sulphur were added at two levels corresponding to 200 and 100 ppm for N and P and 40 and 20 ppm with respect to S. Nitrogen in the form $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, phosphorus as KH_2PO_4 and sulphur as K_2SO_4 were added.

Sulphate sulphur content in the soil at each stage was extracted with 0.15% calcium chloride solution (Kwalenko and Lowe⁸) and determined by the reduction method of Johnson and Nishita⁶. The effect of added salts of N, P or S on the sulphur mineralisation from the native soil organic matter was calculated by subtracting the value of control from the corresponding treated samples.

Results and Discussion

The two soils used in this study indicated considerable differences in their chemical properties (Table 1). Organic sulphur content of Mundabasti soil was 218.1 ppm whereas, that of Chinsurah soil was 49.7 ppm. But 0.15% CaCl_2 extractable sulphate sulphur was found to be much higher in Chinsurah (12.8 ppm) than that in Mundabasti (0.6 ppm) soil.

Inorganic salt of Nitrogen :

Addition of nitrogen as $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ caused a decrease in the mineralisation of sulphur from the

native soil organic matter over the untreated control. This was observed in both the soils, at both the levels of added nitrogen and at all the five stages of sampling over 75 day period of incubation (Table 2). Since nitrogen and sulphur exist in close relationship in soil organic matter, many workers (Freney and Spencer⁷ and Williams⁹) viewed that the mineralisation of sulphur would be similar to that of nitrogen. Hence N : S ratio of the soil may affect the amount of sulphur mineralised in the same way as C : N ratio affect the amount of nitrogen mineralised. Addition of nitrogen increased the N : S ratio in both the soils and hence a decrease in the rate of sulphur mineralisation was noted in the soils. The observed results are in agreement with those of Kwalenko and Lowe⁸. The extent of sulphur immobilisation was more intense in Chinsurah soil than that in Mundabasti soil. Addition of 200 ppm of $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ caused the N : S ratio of Chinsurah soil to increase from 11.4 to 14.6, whereas, it increased from 19.3 to 20.2 in Mundabasti soil. This might explain the observed variation between the two soils.

Inorganic salt of Phosphorus :

Inorganic phosphate addition resulted in immobilisation of available sulphate sulphur in Mundabasti soil (Column B of Table 3). Increasing the level of phosphate resulted in higher amount of sulphur immobilisation. These were observed at all the five stages of sampling over the 75 day period of incubation. Whereas, an increase in the amount

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF INORGANIC SALT OF SULPHUR ADDITION ON SULPHUR MINERALISATION

Soil samples collected from	Levels of S-added (ppm)	S-mineralised (ppm)									
		Incubation period in days									
		15		30		45		60		75	
		A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B
Mundabasti	40	4.69	-0.93	1.87	-0.32	2.81	0	2.19	-1.25	2.50	-0.62
	20	5.31	-0.31	1.12	-1.07	1.87	-0.94	0.62	-2.82	1.25	-1.87
Chinsurah	40	25.62	10.00	25.31	15.93	21.25	12.81	16.87	10.00	19.06	11.25
	20	13.75	-1.87	14.06	4.68	12.19	3.75	10.31	3.44	12.81	5.00

A=Sulphate sulphur content

B=Increase of sulphate sulphur over control.

of available sulphate sulphur over the control (mineralisation) was observed under the similar situation in Chinsurah soil. In the first one month period of incubation the said increase was higher at the higher level of phosphorus application (200 ppm). In the subsequent period, however, the higher amount of sulphur mineralisation was recorded at lower level of added phosphorus. The results thus corroborate the findings of Barrow¹ that mineralisation of sulphur depends on the concentration of added phosphorus. The variation in the nature and amount of the native soil organic matter and its sulphate content might explain the opposite trend of results in Mundabasti and Chinsurah soil.

Inorganic salt of Sulphur :

Corresponding changes in available sulphate sulphur content following the addition of inorganic sulphate (K_2SO_4) to the same two soils are presented in Table 4. Results (Column B) reveal that Mundabasti soil immobilise not only the added sulphate but also the amount of available sulphate sulphur which are already present in the soil. After the first 15 day period of incubation, the extent of sulphur immobilisation was found to be higher at lower level of sulphur addition.

On the other hand, although considerable amount of inorganic sulphur was immobilised in Chinsurah soil, the extent of sulphur immobilisation at no stage exceeded 75% of the 40 ppm level of application (Column B, Table 4). Much higher amount of the added sulphur was immobilised in the Chinsurah soil at 20 ppm level of application. At the initial stage of incubation (15 day period) an amount of 1.87 ppm of available sulphate sulphur over the 20 ppm of added sulphur was

found to be immobilised in the soil. Mineralisation of recently immobilised sulphur was however, noted at the later period of incubation. But the amount mineralised at no stage exceeded 25% of the added amount (20 ppm). Hesse⁹ however, observed increased sulphate formation in a forest soil following the addition of sulphur as $CaSO_4$ over 30 day period of incubation. On the other hand, results of laboratory incubation studies of Barrow¹ indicated that with low levels of sulphur supply there was a tendency of mineralisation of sulphate and after the initial lag phase in microbial development was over mineralisation of sulphur occurred in the soil.

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